

HISTORY OF CONSTRUCTION OF PACHKAMAR WATER RESERVOIR

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ANNOTATION: The article, based on archival and primary sources, reveals the history of the construction of the reservoir during the years of Soviet power in the Kashkadarya oasis, as well as the development of new lands and the history of the irrigation system. The volume, results and consequences of the work done during the construction of reservoirs are illuminated by historical evidence.

KEY WORDS: Soviet power, agricultural policy, reservoir, irrigation, development, Pachkamar, raw materials, project,

The research work was carried out on the basis of generally accepted historical methods - historicity, comparative logical analysis, consistency, principles of impartiality, in which sources on the development of new lands and the history of the irrigation system in the Kashkadarya oasis were studied. It is believed that many sources are involved in scientific circulation.

During the years of Soviet power, serious attention was paid to the development of the irrigation system in the republic, as a result of which many reservoirs were built. These creative works, in turn, made it possible to collect and preserve water supplies for irrigation. However, their excessive construction was closely related to the then cotton monopoly policy of the center, and the irrigation sector was aimed at developing cotton growing. The natural conditions and capabilities of the republic were almost not taken into account during the construction of water bodies. For this reason, the excessive construction of waterworks has naturally caused environmental problems. However, the Soviet authorities did not pay attention to such problems. They were only interested in growing cotton and obtaining a higher yield, as well as transporting the finished raw material to the center.

It is known that in areas where natural sources of water are insufficient, water structures are built to supply the land with water. Kashkadarya region is a region located on the southern borders of Uzbekistan, and the presence of a favorable geographical environment, fertile lands and large areas makes it possible to grow fertile agricultural products here. But at the same time, the only problem of the oasis is the lack of natural sources of water. Today, we manage to

grow agricultural products in the country only through the use of existing water bodies and the use of modern technologies for providing water to the land.

Reservoirs are the most important water source for the country's water supply. Reservoirs are artificial lakes created by man in the bed of a river or stream, in a depression or depression on the surface of the earth through dams and various barriers. Reservoirs are built with the aim of distributing river flow over the seasons and controlling floods in accordance with the water needs of industry, agriculture, the local population, transport and other sectors of the economy [1].

The largest works in these years were carried out in the water sector. Large reservoirs were built in the Kashkadarya oasis to meet the water needs of areas experiencing water shortages during the development of the Karshi desert. In particular, on October 21, 1960, a resolution of the Council of Ministers of Uzbekistan "On the construction of the Pachkamar reservoir" was adopted[2]. The Ministry of Land Reclamation and Water Management of the Uzbek SSR instructed the Uzgiprovodkhoz Institute to develop this project - the construction of a reservoir. Chief Engineer K.K. The project, worth 14,349.05 thousand rubles, drawn up by Pisarchik, was approved on November 3, 1961 [3]. Before the construction of the structure, only 20 thousand hectares of the 55 thousand hectares of land available in the Guzor region were irrigated [4].

The health project of the Bolshaya Ora Guzordarya water storage facility with a capacity of 260 million cubic meters of water has been built. The cost of construction of the object is 17.3 million rubles. Pervonachalno k stroitelnyam rabotam pristupilo upravlenie "Chimkurgankurilish". In 1964, according to the Ministry of Water Management and Water Management of the Uzbek SSR, the document of the Committee on the introduction and exploitation of the Pachkamar water supply facility was approved in the amount of 178,465 rubles. Construction work was completed in 1963. In 1964, the work was accelerated, and the construction was completed. In 1965, it was reorganized into the department "Pachkamarsuvkurilish" under the management of "Chimkurgankurilish" and "Karshisuvkurilish". Administration vo glave s A.Yu. shcherbakovym zavershila stroitelstvo vodokhranilishcha [5]. On December 29, 1967, 100 million cubic meters of water were released from the Pachkamar water supply. In 1968, the water supply system was installed in the territory of the Guzor district. Vveden v stroy October 12, 1969. In the Guzorsky district, water security is increased by 5 thousand hectares of arable land, the possibility of cultivation of 15 thousand hectares of new land appears, and the production

of agricultural products is increased. For example, in Guzorskoy district in 1966. bylo proizvedeno 7200 t of cotton, a v 1970 g. etot pokazatel sostavil pochni 30 000 t [6]. As a result of the Chimkurgan and Pachkamar water supply constructions, 80 million cubic meters of water were built in 1961, and 500 million cubic meters of water were built in 1969 [7].

Irrigated areas expanded and the region's cotton production plan increased. Thanks to the measures taken to improve the state of irrigation in the region in 1964-1966, cotton yields increased by 23.5 centners per hectare, and in 1966 the total volume of cotton production amounted to 217.3 thousand tons, i.e. by 23 thousand. tons more than in 1965. 3 thousand tons was a lot [8].

In order to improve water supply to the irrigated areas of the oasis, the Center increased the construction of hydraulic structures in the project and reconstructed existing ones. A large number of water intakes from irrigation sources without hydraulic structures made water regulation difficult. Only 99 out of 240 water intakes from sources in the oasis were built with engineering structures [9]. This situation has made us think about measures to prevent water seepage into the irrigated lands of the oasis due to water wastage.

To ensure the implementation of the decision of the Government of Uzbekistan dated May 12, 1967, capital funds in the amount of 301.4 million rubles were allocated, and 52.2 million rubles were spent on construction and installation work. It was decided to spend 161.4 million rubles on the construction of the main canal, and 122.4 million rubles on construction and installation work[10].

In 1967, organizations responsible for the development of the desert completed construction and installation work by 17% more than in 1966[11]. In 1967, as a result of measures taken to clean irrigation networks, supply water to fields and prevent excessive water use in the Upper Kashkadarya regions, water supply to irrigated lands was relatively improved. The plan was implemented in the collective farms of Shakhrisabz, Chirakchi, and Kamashi district. The collective farms of the Koson region did not fulfill the plan[12]. The reason was that there were many problems with the supply of water to the cultivated fields. The work carried out did not produce results. The main attention was paid to the development of the Karshi desert. Work to supply water to the lower reaches of the Kashkadarya River has been accelerated.

The Center made many decisions on the construction of irrigation structures and strictly controlled their implementation. However, in most cases these plans turned out to be unpromising, and the complex of construction of the

irrigation system was forced to be implemented. Appointments of an essentially colonial nature increased every year. In particular, the Chimkurgan, Pachkamar, Talimarjon, and Khisorak reservoirs were built. As a result of the work carried out at the end of the twentieth century in Kashkadarya, new land worth 700 thousand was allocated for agriculture [13].

On behalf of the center, the construction of reservoirs has seriously increased in order to develop reserve and gray lands and irrigate cotton fields. In particular, on October 21, 1960, the Council of Ministers of the USSR adopted a resolution of the Council of Ministers of Uzbekistan "On the construction of the Pachkamar reservoir" [14]. As a result of the construction of the Chimkurgan and Pachkamar reservoirs, instead of 80 million cubic meters of water in 1961, it will be possible to collect 500 million cubic meters of water in 1969 [15].

In addition, the construction of the Old Angor canal, 183 km long, was carried out, diverting water from the Zarafshan River to Kashkadarya. The construction of the Uchkizil reservoir and a large reservoir in the Surkhandarya region, the Tuyabogiz reservoir on the Okhangaron River, has also been accelerated.

In 1957, the volume of Yakkabogdarya was 18 million. m³ of the Kamashi Reservoir, construction of the Chimkurgan Reservoir was completed in 1963. The construction of these facilities was carried out by Uzglavvodstroy. As a result, the water availability of irrigated lands in the Kashkadarya region increased, cotton fields expanded and gross productivity increased. If in 1962 the gross cotton harvest in the region amounted to 139 thousand tons. and in 1966 - 218 thousand tons, or 57% more.

In 1957, the construction of the Kamashi reservoir with a volume of 18 million m³ was completed in Yakkabogdarya, and in 1963, the Chimkurgan reservoir. The construction of these facilities was carried out by Uzglavvodstroy. As a result, the water availability of irrigated lands in the Kashkadarya region increased, cotton fields expanded and gross productivity increased. If in 1962 the gross cotton harvest in the region amounted to 139 thousand tons. and in 1966 - 218 thousand tons, or 57% more.

In the early 1960s, a number of large-scale measures in the field of water engineering were developed and implemented. 500 million in the middle reaches of Kashkadarya. The Chimkurgan reservoir was built on m³ of water. Then the volume will be 260 million rubles. The Pachkamar reservoir with a capacity of m³ was put into operation. The Moscow Canal and other large facilities were put into operation.

The rapid development of cotton growing in Kashkadarya and the construction of a water pipeline included in it were inextricably linked with the colonial policy of the Soviet state in the agricultural sector. For these purposes, over the past 60 years, the area of irrigated land in the republic has tripled. Large reservoirs have been built, such as Chimkurgan (500 million m³), Pachkamar (200 million m³).

Thanks to the selfless work of Kashkadarya residents, reservoirs with a volume of 500 thousand cubic meters 3 were built in Makridsoy, Kitab district (water was pumped into them by diesel pumps), as well as in Shorobsoy with a volume of 2 million. Toshloksoy-7 million in the Shakhrisabz region, capable of holding cubic meters of water. cubic meters, Frunze - 1.5 million cubic meters. cubic meters, Karabog in the Yakkabog region - 7.5 million cubic meters. cubic meters, Yangikorgon - 3.3 million cubic meters, Nogaili - 3.0 million cubic meters, Kyzylsuv - 9.5 million cubic meters. cubic meters, Kalkama, Chirakchi district - 9.45 million. cubic meter, in the Kamashi district, Gamashi - 25 million cubic meters. cubic meters, Langara - 7.25 million cubic meters, Dekhkonabad district, Dekhkonabad city 8.2 million cubic meters. cubic meter tanks were built.

The policy on the construction of reservoirs was not relaxed at all, but became stricter every year. In particular, thanks to the construction of irrigation in the region in 1971-1990, the number of operating reservoirs in the region reached 13. The construction of 3 reservoirs continued, and design work for the 1st reservoir was completed. From all the above information, it is known that the goal of the Soviet government in constructing reservoirs in the oasis was to establish regular irrigation of irrigated lands and improve cotton production. Accumulating water resources for continuous irrigation of large cotton fields was considered a very important issue for the Soviets. However, in a number of cases, the above irrigation construction measures were not fully implemented. The reason for this was that during the construction of many irrigation structures, local conditions and the ecological situation of the republic were not taken into account, while at the same time other tasks were determined from the center and their implementation was made a condition before the only facility was completely built.

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